

ANALYSIS OF RETAINING WALL BEHAVIOR UNDER STATIC AND DYNAMIC LOADING CONDITIONS USING SAP2000

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Abstract

To analyses the behavior of earth retaining structures under different conditions has been very important issue due to their wide applications in several infrastructural applications and other structures. The problem of instability of walls is mainly related to earth pressure distribution on the wall and the response of wall against the earth pressure, especially, under dynamic loading condition. In this project different load conditions acting on Retaining Wall and make software-based analysis to make downstream things safe by carrying load and analyzing RCC Retaining Wall to sustained load of upstream backfill under different condition and check the things derived on software with casted model.

Keywords: RCC T-shaped cantilever Retaining Wall, SAP2000, Stability check for different loading condition.

1. INTRODUCTION

A retaining wall is a structure used to retain earth or other materials and to maintain ground surface at different elevations at either side of it. Retaining walls are used to retain earth or other materials which have the tendency to slide and repose at a particular inclination. They provide lateral support to the backfill, embankment or in order to hold them in a vertical position. High R. C. C. retaining walls may be used economically by providing on the backfill side of the wall. Such walls may be termed as the Retaining Wall. A retaining wall or retaining structure is used for maintaining the ground surfaces at different elevations on either side of it. Whenever embankments are involved in construction, retaining wall are usually necessary. In the construction of buildings having basements, retaining walls are mandatory.

2. CANTILEVER RETAINING WALL

Figure 1 Cantilever Retaining Wall

Types of Retaining Wall

- Gravity Wall
- Cantilever Retaining wall
- T-shaped
- L-shaped
- Counterfort Retaining wall
- Buttressed Retaining wall

- Forces Acting on Retaining Wall
- Lateral Earth Pressure

There are three types of lateral load applied on a retaining wall based on the behavior of the wall.

Active Earth Pressure

Force applied by the soil on the wall when the wall is free to deflect. In other words, for ease of understanding, we say soil moves towards the wall.

Active pressure is calculated from the following equation.

$$p_a = k_a \gamma h$$

k_a -active pressure coefficient

$$= \frac{(1 - \sin\theta)}{1 + \sin\theta}$$

γ -density of soil and h -height of the wall

Passive Earth Pressure

Pressure earth pressure is developed when the wall is pressing the soil. Here, we say, wall moving towards the soil for ease of understanding.

Passive earth pressure can be calculated from the following equation.

$$p_p = k_p \gamma h$$

k_p -passive pressure coefficient

$$= \frac{(1 + \sin\theta)}{1 - \sin\theta}$$

γ -density of soil and h -height of the wall

At Rest Pressure or At Rest Condition

This is a special case and the pressure varies between the active pressure and the passive pressure. When we say at rest, we assume structure does not move. Therefore, the pressure applied to the wall increase than the active pressure.

Surcharge Loads

The surcharge is a pressure load applied to the soil retained by the wall. It could be a form of line load or uniformly distributed load

Water Pressure

It is very important to be altered on the forces acting on a retaining wall due to the pore water pressure. Incorrect estimation of the water pressure could lead to failures as discussed in the article retaining wall failures.

Axial Forces Action on Retaining Wall

If there are other structures supported on the retaining wall, we have to consider their effect on the design.

Wind Loads

Usually, wind loads are not that critical for retaining walls. However, when there are other constructions on the free-standing retaining wall, it could affect stability. For example, tall boundary walls built on the wall could have some effect. But it might not be that critical.

Earthquake Loads

Earthquake forces acting on a retaining wall has a considerable impact on the stability of the retaining wall.

We calculate the earth pressure coefficient (active pressure, passive pressure, at rest pressure) and then estimate the applied load Impact Loads such as Accidental Loads, Blast Loads, etc. Impact loads are not that common for retaining walls. They could be applied very rare Further, there is less chance of applying those loads against the stability as if there is a high chance of applying the pressing in the exposed surface which generates restore moment. However, retaining walls could damage due to these types of loads.

Other Forces

When the retaining walls are constructed on the other structure considering it as the foundation of the wall, there may be additional stress on the wall.

For example, if we constructed the retaining wall on the raft foundation as the basement wall when loads are applied on the raft foundation, some stress will be transferred to the wall due to the stiffness of the wall

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following researchers have carried out the study related to the dissertation topic.

Prachi S Bhojar, Dr. G. D. Awachat presents the results of static analysis and design of retaining wall with and without shelves. The conclusions in this thesis drawn based on the discussion and results obtained analytically and using a staad-pro model study. The pressure distribution diagram changes substantially due to the addition of shelves. The overturning moment gets reduced

due to provision of relief shelves. It is also observed that the saving in cost of construction is 15% to 25% by the provision of relief shelves over the conventional cantilever retaining wall. There is 35% saving in concrete and 11% saving in steel.

Prof. Shilpi Bhuniyan, Ms. Bhagyashree Girme, Mr. Bilal Lambe and Mr. Aditya Agrawal This paper concerned with comparison of structural analysis of cantilever retaining wall along with different position of relief shelf are studied in details such as compare load on shelf and displacement on nodes of retaining wall with relief shelves using STAAD-PRO. The retaining wall with a relief shelf is proved to be advantageous over the cantilever and counter fort retaining wall. The best location for the single shelf is observed to be between 0.4h to 0.5h for the maximum reduction in earth pressure, less bending moment and less deflection. Flection.

A. C. Chougule, Prof. J. P. Patankar, P. A. Chougule This paper conducts a thorough analysis of the design measure taken of reinforced concrete cantilever retaining walls with single, double and without shelves. Manual and software analysis is done. Software analysis is done by using STAAD Pro V8i software. Retaining walls with shelves are economical compared to conventional retaining walls without shelves. In retaining wall with shelves, as the height of the wall increases, the percentage saving of material increases. Cantilever retaining walls with two shelves are economical as compared to cantilever walls with single shelf.

Hany F. Shehata This paper presents a Finite Element analysis of retaining wall using PLAXIS2D-AE.01. The reduced total active earth pressure due to the provisioning of shelves is depicted. It was found that the shelves had a significant effect on the resulting earth pressure distribution. This decrease enables the retaining structures to become more stable and to exhibit lower bending moments. The shelves significantly decrease the maximum bending moment and the top movement of the wall. This decrease in the lateral pressure increases the retaining structure stability.

V. B. Chauhan, S. M. Dasaka Present study attempts to investigate the possible reasons behind the failure of a cantilever retaining wall with relief shelves, which is located in the heart of Hyderabad city, India. In the present analysis, rigid retaining walls with five relief shelves provided at different heights of wall having equal widths are analyzed with FLAC3D. It is found that the use of a larger width of relief shelves has significantly increased bending stress in relief shelf as well as on the faces of stem of wall just the relief shelves. These unanticipated stresses might have been neglected in the designs, resulting in failure of retaining wall.

Prof. Sarita Singla, Er. Sakshi Gupta In this paper the study of the behavior and optimal design of three types of reinforced concrete walls of varying heights namely cantilever retaining wall, counter fort retaining wall and retaining wall with relieving platforms is done. The retaining wall with a relieving platform is proved to be most cost-effective and advantageous over the cantilever and counter fort retaining wall. Due to discontinuous lateral earth pressure diagram in case of retaining wall

with relieving platform, there is better stability in the retaining wall.

Problem Statement

Retaining walls can prevent soil from falling down a slope. They can also prevent dirt from falling down a slope and out from under your property. Both of these situations are very serious, and a retaining wall may be the only barrier between backfill.

So, we need to study the pressure forces acting on the retaining wall and to analyses backfill pressure for different condition on same so that, we can design most preferable retaining wall that can retain soil mass in various conditions like landslide, earthquake etc. It can be done using software-based analysis and implementation on same.

4. OBJECTIVE

- Analysis of retaining wall using SAP 2000 software.
- Analyse retaining wall for different backfill conditions i.e.
- Dry backfill
- Semi-Dry backfill
- Wet backfill
- Analysis of Retaining Wall for different backfill conditions and to check software model results with casted model for different loading condition

Research Methodology

Data Collection

Data collection is process where we get an idea to work on our project, where we collected data requirements, problems and how can we solve those problems So, by collecting data from retaining wall site situated at

Near Godavari River, Chopra lawns, Nashik 423002

The site is located at river face at which Retaining wall facing on one side and other end is full of backfill in this situation the weep hole provided in Retaining Wall get chocked up due to backfill i.e. clay soil get packed in weep hole so the pressure due to saturated mass of soil in backfill increases and deflection of wall take place.

In other side if water level at river face increases the saturated pressure of water and the backfill load compresses barrier i.e. Retaining wall

Mango estate project-Bombay Naka, Nashik 423005

On this site Retaining wall is constructed to have a barrier to sustained backfill at 7m from foundation. The backfill is totally earth mass and suffered with some landslide condition. To retain downstream site safely the design of Retaining Wall is made

5. DESIGN

Height of cantilever wall from ground level	=	4.00 m
Unit weight of Earth	γ	= 18 kN/m ³ = 18000 N/m ²
Angle of repose	=	30 Degree
Safe Bearing capacity of soil	q_0	= 100 kN/m ²
Coefficient of friction	μ	= 0.5 = 25 N/mm ²
Concrete	f_c	= M 20
Steel	f_s	= 415
Nominal cover	=	30 mm
Surcharge angle	β	= 16 Degree
Foundation depth	=	1.00 m

1 Design Constants:- For HYSD Bars Concrete M = 20

$$\sigma_{st} = 230 \text{ N/mm}^2 \quad \text{wt. of concrete} = 25000 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

$$\sigma_{cbc} = 7 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

$$m = 13.33$$

$$k = \frac{m^2 c}{m^2 c + \sigma_{st}} = \frac{13.33 \times 7}{13.33 \times 7 + 230} = 0.289$$

$$j = 1 - k/3 = 1 - 0.289 / 3 = 0.904$$

$$R = 1/2 \times c \times j \times k = 0.5 \times 7 \times 0.904 \times 0.289 = 0.913$$

Figure 2 Design of T shaped Cantilever Retaining Wall

$$\sin \beta = 0.276 \quad \cos \beta = 0.96 \quad \tan \beta = 0.29$$

$$\sin \phi = 0.5 \quad \cos \phi = 0.87$$

$$K_a = \cos \beta \frac{\cos \beta - \sqrt{\cos^2 \beta - \cos^2 \phi}}{\cos \beta + \sqrt{\cos^2 \beta - \cos^2 \phi}} = 0.96 \times \frac{0.961 - \sqrt{0.92 - 0.75}}{0.961 + \sqrt{0.92 - 0.75}} = 0.38$$

For surcharge wall, The ratio of length of slabs (DE) to base width b is given by eq.

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{q_0}{2.7 \gamma H} = 1 - \frac{100}{2.7 \times 18 \times 5.00} = 0.59 \text{ Eq (1)}$$

The base width is given by Eq.

$$b = H \times \frac{K_a \cos \beta}{\sqrt{(1-\alpha) \times (1+3\alpha)}}$$

$$b = 5.00 \times \frac{0.38 \times 0.961}{\sqrt{(1 - 0.59) \times (1 + 1.77)}} = 2.83 \text{ m}$$

The base width from the consideration of sliding is given by Eq.

$$b = \frac{0.7 H K_a}{(1-\alpha) \mu} = \frac{0.7 \times 5.00 \times 0.38}{(1 - 0.59) \times 0.5} = 6.45 \text{ m}$$

This width is excessive. Normal practice is to provide b between 0.4 to 0.6 H.

Taking maximum value of H = 0.6 b = 0.60 x 5.00 = 3.00 m

Hence Provided b = 3.00 m

The wall will be unsafe against sliding. This will be made safe by providing a shear Key at base.

Width of toe slab = $\alpha \times b = 0.59 \times 3.00 = 1.77 \text{ m}$ Provided toe slab = 1.80 m

Let the thickness of base = H/12 = 5.00 / 12 = 0.42 or say = 0.40 m

Hence width of heel slab = 3.00 - 0.40 - 1.80 = 0.80 m

Figure 3 Dimension of Base

Height AB = 5.00 - 0.40 = 4.60 m consider 1 m length of retaining wall

$$\text{Maximum Bending moment at B} = \frac{K \times \gamma \times H^2}{2} = \frac{0.38 \times 18 \times (4.60)^2}{2} = 72.27 \text{ KN-m}$$

Hence the horizontal earth pressure is $P_H = P \cos \beta = 72.27 \times 0.961 = 69 \text{ kN}$

$$\text{B.M. at B} = P_H \times \frac{H_1}{3} = 69.00 \times \frac{4.60}{3} = 105.8 \text{ kN}$$

$$\text{Effective depth required} = \sqrt{\frac{\text{BM}}{R \times b}} = \sqrt{\frac{105.80 \times 10^6}{0.913 \times 1000}} = 340 \text{ mm}$$

Keep d = 350 mm and total thickness = 350 + 60 = 410 mm

Assuming that 12 mm ϕ bar will be used. a nominal cover of = 60 - 6 = 54 mm

Reduce the total thickness = 300 mm at top so that effective depth of = 240 mm

$$t_v = \frac{69 \times 1000}{1000 \times 350} = 0.197 \text{ N/mm}^2 > t_c \text{ even at minium steel}$$

Figure 4 Thickness of Stem

Length of heel slab = 3.00 - 1.80 - 0.41 = 0.79 m

Height $H_2 = H_1 + L_2 \tan \beta = 4.60 + 0.79 \times 0.29 = 4.83 \text{ m}$

Height H = 4.83 + 0.40 = 5.23 m

$$\text{Earth pressure } p = \frac{K_a \times \gamma \times H^2}{2} = \frac{0.38 \times 18 \times (5.23)^2}{2} = 93.29 \text{ kN} \dots (2)$$

$$P_H = P \cos \beta = 93.29 \times 0.96 = \text{####} \text{ kN}$$

$$P_V = P \sin \beta = 93.29 \times 0.28 = \text{####} \text{ kN}$$

P is acting on vertical face BC_1 at M_3 and hence P_V will act at vertical line

Full dimension wall is shown in fig 1a

Let W_1 = weight of rectangular portion of stem

W_2 = weight of triangular portion of stem

W_3 = weight of base slab

W_4 = weight of soil on heel slab.

The calculation are arranged in Table

Detail	force(kN)	lever arm	Moment about toe (kN-m)
W_1 1 x 0.30 x 4.60 x 25 =	34.5	2.06	71.07
W_2 1/2 x 0.11 x 4.60 x 25 =	6.33	1.855	11.73
W_3 1 x 3.00 x 0.40 x 25 =	30	1.5	45
W_4 1 x 0.80 x 4.71 x 18 =	67.87	2.6	176.46
W_5	P_1	3.00	77.13
	ΣW		164.41
			total M_2 381.40

Total resisting moment = 381.40 kN-m

Figure 5 Stability of Wall

Over turning Over turning moment $M_o = 93.3 \times \frac{5}{3} = 163 \text{ kN-m}$
 \therefore F.S. against over turning $= \frac{-381.40}{162.53} = 2.35 > 2$ Hence safe
 F.S. against Sliding $= \frac{\mu \Sigma W}{P_H} = \frac{0.5 \times 164.41}{89.67} = 0.92 < 1.5$
 Hence not safe, To make safe against sliding will have to provide shear key
Pressure distribution net moment $\Sigma M = 381.40 - 163 = 218.87 \text{ kN-m}$
 \therefore Distance \bar{x} of the point of application of resultant, from toe is
 $\bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma M}{\Sigma W} = \frac{218.87}{164.41} = 1.33 \text{ m}$
 $\frac{b}{2} - \bar{x} = \frac{3.00}{2} - 1.33 = 0.17 \text{ m} < 0.5$ Hence safe
 Eccentricity $e = \frac{b}{2} - \bar{x} = \frac{3.00}{2} - 1.33 = 0.17 \text{ m} < 0.5$ Hence safe
 Pressure p_1 at toe $= \frac{\Sigma W}{b} \left(1 + \frac{6e}{b} \right) = \frac{164.41}{3.00} \times \left(1 + \frac{6 \times 0.17}{3.00} \right) = 100 \text{ kN-m}^2$ Hence safe
 Pressure p_2 at Heel $= \frac{\Sigma W}{b} \left(1 - \frac{6e}{b} \right) = \frac{164.41}{3.00} \times \left(1 - \frac{6 \times 0.17}{3.00} \right) = 100 \text{ kN-m}^2$ Hence safe
 Pressure p at the junction of stem with toe slab
 $p = 73.30 - \frac{73.30 - 36.31}{3.00} \times 1.80 = 40.8 \text{ kN-m}^2$
 Pressure p' at the junction of stem with Heel
 $p' = 73.30 - \frac{73.30 - 36.31}{3.00} \times 0.80 = 40.8 \text{ kN-m}^2$

Figure 6 Stability of Wall (1)

The upward pressure distribution on the toe slab is shown in fig 7b. The weight of soil above the toe slab is neglected. Thus two forces are acting on it

(1) Upward soil pressure (2) Downward weight of slab
 Downward weight of slab per unit area $= 0.40 \times 1 \times 100 \times 25 = 10.00 \text{ kN-m}^2$
 Hence net pressure intensities will be $= 73.30 - 10.00 = 63.30 \text{ kN-m}^2$ under D
 And at under $E = 51.10 - 10.00 = 41.10 \text{ kN-m}^2$
 Total force $=$ S.F. at $E = 0.50 \times (63.30 + 41.10) \times 1.80 = 89.67 \text{ kN}$
 \bar{x} from $E = \frac{(41.10 + 63.30) \times 1.80}{2} = 0.96 \text{ m}$
 \therefore B.M. at $E = 89.67 \times 0.96 = 90.55 \text{ kN-m}$
Effective depth required $= \sqrt{\frac{B.M.}{R_{fb}}} = \sqrt{\frac{90.55 \times 10^4}{0.913 \times 1000}} = 315 \text{ mm}$
 Keep effective depth $d = 320 \text{ mm}$ and total thickness $= 320 + 60 = 380 \text{ mm}$
 reduce the total thickness $= 300 \text{ mm}$ or 0.30 m at edge say $= 0.38 \text{ m}$
 $r_s = \frac{380 \times 1000}{1000 \times 380} = 0.25 \text{ N/mm}^2 < r_{s, \text{even at minium steel}}$
 $A_{st} = \frac{B.M. \times 10^4}{\sigma_{st} \times j \times d} = \frac{90.55 \times 10^4}{230 \times 0.904 \times 320} = 1362 \text{ mm}^2$
 The reinforcement has to be provided at bottom face. If alternate bars of stem reinforcement are bent and continued in toe slab, area available $= 12 \times 1615 = 807.5 \text{ mm}^2$ (see step 7)
 using Φ mm bars $A = \frac{3.14 \times d^2}{4} \times n = \frac{3.14 \times 12^2 \times 12}{4} = 113 \text{ mm}^2$
 \therefore Spacing $A \times 1000 / A_{st} = 113 \times 1000 / 1362 = 80 \text{ mm}$
 Hence Provided $12 \text{ mm } \Phi$ bar, @ 80 mm c/c
 Let us check this reinforcement for development length $L_d = 45 \times 12 = 540 \text{ mm}$
 Providing 30 mm clear side cover actual length available $= 1800 - 30 = 1770 \text{ mm}$
 $1770 > 540$ Hence safe
 Distribution steel $= \frac{0.12}{100} \times 1000 \times \left(\frac{380 + 300}{2} \right) = 408 \text{ mm}^2$

Figure 7 Design of toe Slab

Three force act on it

1. down ward weight of soil 2. weight of heel slab 3. Down ward earth pressure 4. upward soil pressure
 Total weight of soil over Heel $= 0.80 \times \frac{4.60 + 4.83}{2} \times 18 = 67.9 \text{ kN}$ say $= 68.00 \text{ kN}$
 Acting at $\frac{(H_1 + 2H_2) \times b}{(H_1 + H_2) \times 3} = \frac{4.60 + 2 \times 4.83}{4.60 + 4.83} \times \frac{0.80}{3} = 0.403 \text{ m}$ from B
 Total weight of heel slab $= 0.80 \times 0.38 \times 1 \times 25 = 7.60 \text{ kN}$
 Acting at 0.40 m from B .
 Earth pressure intensity at $b = K_a \cdot \gamma \cdot H_1$ per unit inclined area, at β to horizontal,
 \therefore Earth pressure at B , on horizontal unit area $= K_a \cdot \gamma \cdot H_1 \cdot \tan \beta$
 Vertical component of this, at $B = K_a \cdot \gamma \cdot H_1 \cdot \tan \beta \cdot \sin \beta$ (1)
 Similarly, Vertical component of earth pressure intensity at $C = K_a \cdot \gamma \cdot H_2 \cdot \tan \beta \cdot \sin \beta$ (2)
 Hence total force due to vertical component of earth pressure is
 $= K_a \cdot \gamma \cdot \frac{(H_1 + H_2)}{2} \times b_1 \tan \beta \times \sin \beta$
 $= \frac{0.38 \times 18}{2} \times (4.60 + 4.83) \times 0.80 \times 0.29 \times 0.28$
 vertical earth pressure is $= 2.04 \text{ kN}$ This Act at 0.40 m from B
 Total upward soil pressure $= 1/2 \times (63.43 + 36.31) \times 0.80 = 39.90 \text{ kN}$
 Acting at $= \frac{(63.43 + 2 \times 36.31) \times 0.80}{(63.43 + 36.31) \times 3} = 0.36 \text{ m}$ from B
 \therefore Total force $=$ S.F. at $B = 89.67 + 7.60 - 39.90 = 57.37 \text{ kN}$
 \therefore B.M. at $B = (68 \times 0.40) + (8 \times 0.40) - (2.04 \times 0.40) - (39.90 \times 0.36) = 16.77 \times 10^6 \text{ N-mm}^2$

Figure 8 Design of Heel Slab

We had earlier assume the thickness of heel slab $a = 0.40 \text{ m}$
 While it has now been fixed as 0.38 m only. Hence revised $H_1 = 5.00 - 0.38 = 4.62 \text{ m}$
 S.F. at $B = p \cos \beta = \frac{K_a \cdot \gamma}{2} H_1^2 = \frac{0.38 \times 18}{2.00} \times (4.62)^2 = 72.90 \text{ kN} = P_H$
 B.M. at $B = \frac{S.F. \times H_1}{3} = \frac{72.90 \times 4.62}{3} = 112.26 \text{ kN-m}$
 Keep effective depth $d = 350 \text{ mm}$ and total thickness $= 350 + 60 = 410 \text{ mm}$
 reduce the total thickness $= 200 \text{ mm}$ or 0.20 m at edge
 $A_{st} = \frac{B.M. \times 10^4}{\sigma_{st} \times j \times D} = \frac{112.26 \times 10^4}{230 \times 0.904 \times 350} = 1543 \text{ mm}^2$
 Using $12 \text{ mm } \Phi$ bars, Area $= \frac{\pi D^2}{4} = \frac{3.14 \times (12)^2}{4} = 113 \text{ mm}^2$
 \therefore Spacing $= \frac{1000 \times 113}{1543} = 73 \text{ mm}$ say $= 70 \text{ mm c/c}$
 Actual A_{st} provided $= 1000 \times \frac{113}{70} = 1615 \text{ mm}^2$

Figure 9 Reinforcement in the Stem

The wall is in unsafe in sliding, and hence shear key will be provided below the stem as shown in fig. Let us provide shear key 300×410 Let P_p be the intensity of passive pressure developed in front of key this intensity P_p depend upon the soil pressure P in front of the key
 $P_p = K_p P = 1/K_a = 1/0.38 = 2.64 \times 51.10 = 134.67 \text{ kN/m}^2$
 \therefore total passive pressure $P_p = P_p \times a = 134.67 \times 0.30 = 40.40 \text{ kN}$
 Sliding force at level $GJ = 0.38 \times \frac{18}{2.00} \times 5.61 \times \cos \beta$
 or $P_H = 3.42 \times 5.61 \times 0.361 = 6.94 \text{ kN}$ (2)
 Weight of the soil between bottom of the base and $GJ = 3.00 \times 18 \times 0.30 = 162 \text{ kN}$
 $\therefore \Sigma W = 162 + 6.94 = 168.94 \text{ kN}$ Refer force calculation table
 hence equilibrium of wall, permitting F.S. $= 1.5$ against sliding we have
 $1.5 = \frac{\mu \Sigma W + P_p}{P_H} = \frac{0.5 \times 168.94 + 40.40}{6.94} = 1.27 > 1.5$ hence not safe
 However, provided minimum value of $a = 300 \text{ mm}$. Keep width of key 410 mm (equal to stem width) it should be noted that passive pressure taken into account above will be developed only when length a given below is available in front of key:
 $a_1 = a \tan \phi = a \tan \left(45 + \frac{\phi}{2} \right) = a \cdot i_s$ where $(45 + \phi/2) =$ shearing angle of passive resistance
 $\therefore a_1 = 0.3 \times (2.64)^{1/2} = 0.487 \text{ m}$ Actual length of the slab available $= 1.80 \text{ m}$
 Hence satisfactory.
 Now size of key $= 300 \times 410 \text{ mm}$
 Actual force to be resisted by the key at F.S. 1.5 is $= 1.5 P_H - \mu \Sigma W$
 $= 1.5 \times 6.94 - 0.5 \times 168.94 = 64.47 \text{ kN}$
 \therefore shear stress $= \frac{64.47 \times 1000}{300 \times 1000} = 0.215 \text{ N/mm}^2$
 Bending stress $= \frac{64.47 \times 150 \times 1000}{16 \times 1000 \times (300)^2}$

Figure 10 Design of Shear Key

Detailing Sheet of Retaining Wall

Figure 11 Detailing Sheet of Retaining Wall

Reinforcement Detailing Sheet of Retaining Wall

Figure 12 Reinforcement Detailing Sheet of Retaining Wall

Analysis Of Retaining Wall by Using SAP2000

Table 1 Analysis of Retaining Wall by Using SAP2000

Sr No.	Description	Value
1.	Height of retain earth	4m
2.	Width of heel	0.9m
3.	Width of toe	1.2m
4.	Thickness of retaining wall	0.3m
5.	Thickness of heel	0.3m
6.	Thickness of toe	0.3m
7.	Thickness of shear key	0.3m
8.	Cover to reinforcement	30mm
9.	Dry unit weight of soil	16kN/m ³
10.	Saturated unit weight of soil	21kN/m ³
11.	Unit weight of water	9.81kN/m ³
12.	Angle of internal friction	30°
13.	Coefficient of active earth pressure	0.38
14.	Concrete grade	M20
15.	Reinforcement grade	Fe415(HYSD)
16.	SBC of Soil	150kN/m

Figure 13 Retaining Wall Terminology

Grade of Concrete and Steel Define

S Material Property Data

General Data
 Material Name and Display Color: M20
 Material Type: Concrete
 Material Grade: M20
 Material Notes: Modify/Show Notes...

Weight and Mass
 Weight per Unit Volume: 24.9926
 Mass per Unit Volume: 2.5485
 Units: KN, m, C

Isotropic Property Data
 Modulus Of Elasticity, E: 22360680.
 Poisson, U: 0.2
 Coefficient Of Thermal Expansion, A: 5.500E-06
 Shear Modulus, G: 9316950.

Other Properties For Concrete Materials
 Concrete Cube Compressive Strength, f_{ck}: 20000.
 Expected Concrete Compressive Strength: 20000.

Figure 14 Material Property Data

S Material Property Data

General Data
 Material Name and Display Color: HYSD415
 Material Type: Rebar
 Material Grade: HYSD Grade 415
 Material Notes: Modify/Show Notes...

Weight and Mass
 Weight per Unit Volume: 76.9729
 Mass per Unit Volume: 7.849
 Units: KN, m, C

Uniaxial Property Data
 Modulus Of Elasticity, E: 2.000E+08
 Poisson, U: 0.3
 Coefficient Of Thermal Expansion, A: 1.170E-05
 Shear Modulus, G:

Other Properties For Rebar Materials
 Minimum Yield Stress, F_y: 415000.
 Minimum Tensile Stress, F_u: 485000.
 Expected Yield Stress, F_{ye}: 456500.
 Expected Tensile Stress, F_{ue}: 533500.

Figure 15 Material Property Data

6. RESULTS

LOAD CALCULATION

1. Only Dry Soil condition

depth (m)	horizontal pressure			Vertical pressure		
	Dry kPa	Submerged kPa	Water kPa	Dry kPa	Submerged kPa	Water kPa
0.4	2.34	0.00	1.43	0.67	0.00	0.00
0.8	4.68	0.00	2.87	1.34	0.00	0.00
1.2	7.01	0.00	4.30	2.01	0.00	0.00
1.6	9.35	0.00	5.73	2.68	0.00	0.00
2.0	11.69	0.00	7.17	3.35	0.00	0.00
2.4	14.03	0.00	8.60	4.02	0.00	0.00
2.8	16.36	0.00	10.03	4.69	0.00	0.00
3.2	18.70	0.00	11.47	5.36	0.00	0.00
3.6	21.04	0.00	12.90	6.03	0.00	0.00
4.0	23.38	0.00	14.33	6.70	0.00	0.00

Figure 16 Load Calculation

2. Dry soil upto half depth and ground water at half depth

depth (m)	horizontal pressure			Vertical pressure		
	Dry kPa	Submerged kPa	Water kPa	Dry kPa	Submerged kPa	Water kPa
0.4	2.34	0.00	0.00	0.67	0.00	0.00
0.8	4.68	0.00	0.00	1.34	0.00	0.00
1.2	7.01	0.00	0.00	2.01	0.00	0.00
1.6	9.35	0.00	0.00	2.68	0.00	0.00
2.0	11.69	1.63	1.43	3.35	0.47	0.41
2.4	14.03	3.27	2.87	4.02	0.94	0.82
2.8	16.36	4.90	4.30	4.69	1.41	1.23
3.2	18.70	6.54	5.73	5.36	1.88	1.64
3.6	21.04	8.17	7.17	6.03	2.34	2.06
4.0	23.38	9.80	8.60	6.70	2.81	2.47

Figure 17 Dry Soil up to half depth and ground water at half depth

3. Submerged soil upto top with ground water at top

depth m	horizontal pressure			vertical pressure		
	Dry kPa	Submerged kPa	Water kPa	Dry kPa	Submerged kPa	Water kPa
0.4	0.00	1.63	1.43	0.67	0.47	0.41
0.8	0.00	3.27	2.87	1.34	0.94	0.82
1.2	0.00	4.90	4.30	2.01	1.41	1.23
1.6	0.00	6.54	5.73	2.68	1.88	1.64
2.0	0.00	8.17	7.17	3.35	2.34	2.06
2.4	0.00	9.81	8.60	4.02	2.81	2.47
2.8	0.00	11.44	10.03	4.69	3.28	2.88
3.2	0.00	13.08	11.47	5.36	3.75	3.29
3.6	0.00	14.71	12.90	6.03	4.22	3.70
4.0	0.00	16.35	14.33	6.70	4.69	4.11

Figure 18 Submerged Soil up to with ground water at top

Load Combinations

Strength case

1.5 load factor to all

Dead load combined with following combinations

1. Full dry soil condition – no water table condition
2. Half dry soil conditio – water table at half the depth of soil to heel
3. Full saturation and submergence - water table at top of soil

Define Load Cases

Load Case Name	Load Case Type
DCAD	Modal
DRYHALF1	Linear Static
SUBHALF1	Linear Static
SUBFULL1	Linear Static
WATHALF1	Linear Static
WATFULL1	Linear Static
1.5(DL+DRYFULL)	Linear Static
1.5(DL+WATHALF)	Linear Static
1.5(DL+WATFULL)	Linear Static

Figure 19 Load Combinations

Figure 20 Soil Pressure-Dry Full (KPa)

Table 2 Result Summary

	Dry backfill	Semi-Dry backfill	Wet backfill
Lateral reaction due to upstream loads	minimum	intermediate	maximum
Concrete section requirement	minimum	intermediate	maximum
Steel reinforcement required	minimum	intermediate	maximum
Safety of downstream	good	best	intermediate
Safety against flood condition water in grace on upstream	poor	best	intermediate

7. CONCLUSIONS

This study provided the insights how water build-up at back of a retaining wall may affect the performance, load and resistance implications in various design scenarios. Typically, it was noted that the let-go system for water in soil retaining structure is key to its structural longevity, economy and downstream assurance of safety for the purpose the wall is retaining the earth on upstream. The deflection occurs on casted retaining wall is zero when dial gauges are mounted at the time of loading on retaining wall at backfill and when we calculate deflection for same loading analytically by moment area method it shows results that deflection is negligible. At different loading condition the behavior of retaining wall is totally depends on condition of backfill weep hole provided in retaining wall and loading pattern.

REFERENCES

- [1] A.C. Chougule, Prof.J.P. Patankar, P. A. Chougule (2017), "Effective use of Shelves in Cantilever Retaining Walls", International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology, Volume: 04 Issue: 07, e-TSSN: 2395-0056, p-ISSN: 2395-0072.
- [2] Dharshan K, Keerthi Gowda B S (2016), "Stability Enhancement of Cantilever Earth Retaining Wall with Pressure Relief Shelf by Soft Computing Technique", Advanced Engineering and Applied Sciences: An International Journal, ISSN 2320–3927.
- [3] Hany F. Shehata (2016), "Retaining Wall with Relief Shelves", International Journal of Advanced Structural Engineering.
- [4] Hitesh Rathi, Dr. G. N. Ronghe (2019), "Optimize Positioning of Relief Shelf in Cantilever Retaining Wall", Global Research and Development Journal for Engineering, e-ISSN: 2455-5703.
- [5] Karthik Babu C, Keerthi Gowda B S (2016), "Analysis of Counter fort Retaining Wall with and without Pressure Relief Shelf using Soft Computing Technique", Science Insights: An International Journal, ISSN 2277–3835.
- [6] Liu Minnan, Liu Fuchen (2018), "Calculation Model of Earth Pressure on Retaining Wall with Relieving Platform", Electronic Journal of Geotechnical Engineering, Vol.23, Bund.02.
- [7] Prachi S. Bhoyar, Dr. G. D. Awachat (2019), "Static Analysis and Design of Retaining Wall with and without Shelve using Software", International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology, Volume: 06 Issue: 05.
- [8] Prof. Sarita Singla, Er. Sakshi Gupta (2015), "Optimization of Reinforced Concrete Retaining Walls of Varying Heights using Relieving Platforms", International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT), Vol. 4 Issue 06, June-2015, ISSN: 2278-0181.